

A Case of Disseminated Tuberculosis with Tuberculous Meningitis Presenting as Acute Reversible Hemiplegia

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ABSTRACT

The most frequent manifestations of CNS (Central nervous system) tuberculosis are tuberculous meningitis and intra-cranial tuberculomas. We present a case of CNS tuberculous (TB) in nonimmunocompromised adolescent who initially presented with hemiparesis and later diagnosed as disseminated tuberculosis.

Clinical follow up is recommended monthly during treatment. Even after treatment completion a 6 monthly follow-up is indicated for 2 years. Clinical follow-up includes assessment of improvement of symptoms, physical examination, adherence to therapy, side effects of drugs, complications and treatment of co-morbid conditions (malnutrition, HIV). Follow-up investigations should be individualized, like liver function tests if hepatotoxicity is suspected. **(5)** For CNS TB, especially tuberculomas, it is recommended to monitor with repeat neuroimaging at 3 months and 9–12 months to monitor response to treatment. According to the clinical and radiological response of the patient, treatment modification can be done. In the initial 3 months of treatment, there can be an increase in the size and number of tuberculomas (paradoxical reaction), and requires continuation of ATT with addition of steroids. Suspicion of treatment failure should be kept in mind, when lesions either increase in size or fail to decrease in size after 3 to 6 months of treatment with appropriate dosing and good adherence. It could be due to Multi Drug Resistant-TB or paradoxical reaction. **(15)**

Complications can be immediate like seizures, raised intracranial tension and vasculitis; short term like hydrocephalus, cranial nerve palsies and diabetes insipidus; and long term like epilepsy, cognitive disability, blindness and stroke. **(9)** Surgical management in the form of ventriculo-peritoneal shunt insertion is indicated for patients at all stages of severity with hydrocephalus or raised intracranial tension not responding to ATT and steroids. **(15)**

INTRODUCTION

Tuberculosis (TB) is a multi-systemic infectious disease caused by *Mycobacterium tuberculosis (MTB)* – involving pulmonary and extrapulmonary sites (1). In Indian children extrapulmonary cases account for 25% of all cases, with the most common cause of death being tubercular meningitis (TBM). (2) The Central Nervous System (CNS) involvement of TB is most commonly in the form of TBM, followed by tuberculoma. TBM and tuberculomas may be present simultaneously in up to 10% of cases (3). CNS TB is more common in children, the immunocompromised and malnourished ones being affected the most. Proper evaluation for early diagnosis, complete characterization of the involvement and timely treatment of CNS TB is essential to prevent the morbidity and mortality.

CASE HISTORY

A 12 years old unimmunized girl, sixth issue of a non-consanguineous marriage presented with the complaints of right sided weakness for last 2 days. She was completely well 20 days back when she developed fever, which was mild to moderate grade, intermittent in nature, not associated with chills & rigor. For this she was treated by a local practitioner. She also developed a swelling in cervical region of neck along with the onset of fever. Suddenly 2 days back, she developed right sided weakness of whole body involving right side of face, right upper and lower limbs. She was not able to walk. She was treated locally for her weakness for one day but her condition didn't improve. There was no history of headache, vomiting, seizures, ear discharge or head trauma. The patient had no history of similar episodes in the past and had not taken any medications in the past. Her bladder & bowel history was normal. There was history that one of her elder sister had pulmonary TB due to which she died 10 months back at the age of 19 years but no documentation was present.

On examination she was conscious, co-operative and oriented. Her vital signs were normal. She had no BCG scar mark. There was a cervical lymph node palpable in the anterior cervical chain on right side of neck, 2cm X 2cm, firm, non-tender and mobile. The respiratory examination revealed crepitation in the middle zone on the right side. Abdomen was soft with no signs of organomegaly. Cardiac examination was normal. Back & spine examination showed no abnormality. Built was poor. There was no sign of meningeal irritation. Right seventh cranial nerve upper motor neuron palsy was present,

evident by drooping of right side corner of mouth, loss of right nasolabial fold, wrinkling of forehead present on both sides. Her taste sensation was intact. Tone of muscles of right side was decreased. Power was of grade 1/5 in right upper and lower limbs while it was 5/5 on the left side. The deep tendon reflexes on the right side were exaggerated as compared to the left. The plantar reflex was of extensor type on the right side. Sensory examination was normal. Gait could not be assessed as she was not able to walk. The fundus examination of eye revealed no abnormality.

Her investigations were as follows- Hb: 10.7 gm/dL, ESR: 12 mm in 1st hour, WBC: 13300/mm³, N: 83%, L: 16%, E: 1%, M: 0%, Platelet: 260000/mm³. Na: 132.82 meq/L, K: 3.72 meq/L, Ca: 8.3 mg/dL, SGPT: 29 IU/L, SGOT: 18 IU/L, S Creatinine: 0.5 mg/dL. FNAC of cervical lymph node was consistent with tubercular lymphadenitis with Ziehl Nielsen's stain positive. Human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) test was negative. Chest X-ray showed patchy parenchymal opacity in right paracardiac region consistent with consolidation. (Figure 1) Tuberculin test was negative.

FIGURE 1: Chest X-ray showing patchy parenchymal opacity in right paracardiac region

CT scan of brain showed an irregular outline hypodense lesion with few enhanced ring in left temporo-parietal region with mass effect and midline shift. Another wedge shaped hypodense lesion in left basal nuclei region. A nodular calcification with surrounding hypodensity in right frontal lobe.

Keeping a probability of involvement of meninges, a lumbar puncture was done. On lumbar puncture, clear cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) was drained under normal pressure. CSF protein was normal (26 mg/dL) and sugar was low (39 mg/dL). CSF cytology showed 8 cells/ μ L (20% polymorphs and 80% lymphocytes). Ziehl Nielsen's staining was positive while by Grams' method was negative. The Xpert[®] MTB/RIF assay of the CSF was negative but the assay of sputum was positive for TB and negative for rifampicin resistance. CSF culture did not show any growth.

MRI of brain was ordered to confirm the findings of CT scan and to know the exact extent of the involvement of the brain. It showed multiple ring enhancing T2 hypointense lesion in the left temporo-parietal lobe with nonenhancing surrounding edema causing mass effect and midline shift – suggestive of caseating tuberculomas. A nodular hyperintense lesion with central pin point hypointense in the right frontal lobe. A wedge shaped lesion in left basal region – suggestive of infarction. There were patchy enhanced lesions – suggestive of cerebritis. (Figure 2)

FIGURE2: MRI of brain showing multiple rim enhancing T2 hypointense lesion in the left temporo-parietal lobe with nonenhancing surrounding edema causing mass effect and midline shift

Thus, a final diagnosis was reached which was disseminated TB (TBM with multiple tuberculomas, right middle zone TB consolidation and right cervical TB lymphadenitis) presenting as right-sided hemiparesis.

The patient was immediately started on four drug anti-tubercular therapy (ATT), mannitol and dexamethasone. Dexamethasone was switched to oral prednisolone and mannitol was replaced by oral acetazolamide after 3 days, and supplemental pyridoxine was also given.

The other family members were also screened for TB and one of her younger sister was also diagnosed with pulmonary TB and was started on standard ATT.

DISCUSSION

Tuberculosis (TB) is a major cause of ill health, one of the top 10 causes of death worldwide and the leading cause of death from a single infectious agent. India is the epicentre of TB and accounts for 26% of the global cases. In 2019, children below 14 years of age formed about 7% of the estimated 2.64 million cases of TB in India. Though extra pulmonary TB accounts for only 22% of the TB cases but CNS TB is an important cause of morbidity and mortality due to TB. The WHO End TB Strategy has two important components: first is 80% reduction in the TB incidence rate (new and relapse cases per 100 000 population per year) and second is 90% reduction in the annual number of TB deaths by 2030, compared with 2015. (4) To achieve these targets, rapid and timely diagnosis of TB cases is necessary which should be followed by the standard ATT given at recommended dose and duration.

CNS TB is one of the most serious form of TB, due to hematogenous spread of *MTB*. It manifests as meningitis, cerebritis, or tuberculomas. There are two stages in development of CNS TB. Initially, small tuberculous lesions (Rich’s foci) develop in the meninges/cerebral cortex. These caseous lesions discharges bacilli in the subarachnoid space and produces exudates. It infiltrates the cortical and meningeal blood vessels and leads to inflammation, obstruction and finally, infarcts. The caseous infiltrates can sometimes even obstruct the normal flow of CSF in the ventricular system and lead to hydrocephalus. (5,6)

A consensus case definition for TBM was proposed in 2010. (Table 1) These criteria are applicable irrespective of the patients’ age, HIV infection status, or resources available. Patients are stratified as definite, probable, and possible diagnosis of TBM as per these criteria. (7)

TABLE 1: Diagnostic criteria for classification of definite, probable, possible, and not tuberculous meningitis

CATEGORIES FOR PATIENTS WITH SUSPECTED TBM	
Clinical entry criteria	Symptoms and signs of meningitis including one or more of the following: headache, irritability, vomiting, fever, neck stiff ness, convulsions, focal neurological deficits, altered consciousness, or lethargy.
Definitive TBM	Patients should fulfil criterion A or B: A) Clinical entry criteria plus one or more of the following: AFB seen in the CSF; <i>MTB</i> cultured from the CSF; or a CSF positive commercial NAAT. B) AFB seen in the context of histological changes consistent with TB in the brain or spinal cord with suggestive symptoms or signs and CSF changes, or visible meningitis (on autopsy)
Probable TBM	Clinical entry criteria plus <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A total diagnostic score ≥ 10 (when cerebral imaging is not available) or <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ≥ 12 (when cerebral imaging is available) plus exclusion of alternative diagnoses. At least 2 points should either come from CSF or cerebral imaging criteria
Possible TBM	Clinical entry criteria plus <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A total diagnostic score of 6–9 (when cerebral imaging is not available) or <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 6–11 (when cerebral imaging is available) plus exclusion of alternative diagnoses Possible TB cannot be diagnosed or excluded without doing a lumbar puncture or cerebral imaging.
Not TBM	Alternative diagnosis established, without a definitive diagnosis of TBM or other convincing signs of dual disease

DIAGNOSTIC CRITERIA

TABLE 2 : Various criterias & score.

<p>Clinical Criteria Symptom duration >5 days Systemic symptoms suggestive of TB (>1 of the following): weight loss/poor weight gain, night sweats, cough >2weeks History of recent (past 1 year) close contact with pulmonary TB or positive tuberculin sensitivity test (only in children <10 years of age) Focal neurological deficit (excluding cranial nerve palsies) Cranial nerve palsy Altered consciousness</p>	<p>Maximum score = 6 4 2 2 1 1 1</p>
<p>CSF Criteria Clear appearance Cells 10–500/μL Lymphocytic predominance >50% Protein concentration >1g/L CSF to plasma glucose ratio <50% or absolute CSF glucose <2.2 mmol/L</p>	<p>Maximum score = 4 1 1 1 1 1</p>
<p>Cerebral Imaging Hydrocephalus Basal meningeal enhancement Tuberculoma Infarct Pre-contrast: basal hyperdensity</p>	<p>Maximum score = 6 1 2 2 1 2</p>
<p>Evidence of tuberculosis elsewhere Chest radiograph suggestive of signs of active TB: signs of TB=2; miliary TB=4 CT, MRI or Ultrasound evidence for TB outside the CNS AFB identified or <i>MTB</i> cultured from another source (i.e., sputum, lymph node, gastric washing, urine, and blood culture) Positive commercial <i>MTB</i> NAAT from extra neural specimen</p>	<p>Maximum score = 4 2/4 2 4 4</p>
<p>Exclusion of alternative diagnoses An alternative diagnosis must be confirmed microbiologically (by stain, culture, or NAAT when appropriate), serologically (eg, syphilis), or histopathologically (eg, lymphoma). The list of alternative diagnoses that should be considered, dependent upon age, immune status, and geographical region, include: pyogenic bacterial meningitis, cryptococcal meningitis, syphilitic meningitis, viral meningo-encephalitis, cerebral malaria, parasitic or eosinophilic meningitis (<i>Angiostrongylus cantonesis</i>, <i>Gnathostoma spinigerum</i>, toxocariasis, cysticercosis), cerebral toxoplasmosis and bacterial brain abscess (space-occupying lesion on cerebral imaging) and malignancy (eg, lymphoma)</p>	

TB=tuberculosis, TBM= tuberculous meningitis, *MTB*= *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, CSF=cerebrospinal fluid, CNS=central nervous system, NAAT=nucleic acid amplification test, AFB=acid-fast bacilli

Tuberculin Skin Test may be not reactive in 50% cases. Chest X-ray found normal in 20-50% cases. Still it is essential to look for extracranial lesions as it may be helpful for the diagnosis of TBM. WHO endorsed Xpert MTB/ rifampicin (RIF), an automated rapid nucleic acid amplification test (NAAT) for *MTB* in 2010. It detects *MTB* and RIF resistance simultaneously in almost less than 2h. It has a sensitivity of 67%–85% and a specificity of 94%–98%, it is a definitive diagnostic test. However, the role of Xpert MTB/RIF in diagnosing TBM remains limited, because even though a positive result confirms the diagnosis of TBM but a negative result cannot be used to “rule out” TBM. **(8, 9)**

During the hematogenous spread from the lungs, when there is a sizeable inoculation with inadequate cell-mediated immunity, the parenchymal lesion may develop into a tuberculoma. Tuberculoma are firm, spherical and avascular mass between 2 to 10cm with edema and gliosis, which are formed by aggregation of caseous tubercle that usually manifest clinically as intracranial space occupying lesion (ICSOL). (10) In adults they are frequently supratentorial while in children infratentorial in location. (11) Tuberculoma usually presents as headache, seizure, focal neurologic deficits & papilledema. They may present months to years after infection. They may develop early during infection or anytime during treatment.

On CT scan, tuberculomas appear as low- or high-density round or lobulated masses with irregular walls showing homogenous enhancement after contrast administration. The radiographic appearance of tuberculomas is divided in non-caseating, caseating with a solid center or caseating with a liquid center. The degree of perilesional edema has been

described as being inversely proportional to duration of the lesion. (12) Magnetic resonance spectroscopy has been suggested as a method to distinguish tuberculomas from cysticercosis. (13)

CNS TB may present with symptoms & signs that are nonspecific, leading sometimes to misdiagnosis. This patient presented with history of fever of 20 days and right sided complete hemiparesis of 2 days duration with no history of headache, vomiting, seizure & altered sensorium. Chest X-ray of the patient showed right middle zone opacities which may be consistent with TB consolidation. The FNAC of cervical lymphadenitis was consistent with TB. Sputum and family history of contact was also positive for TB. Though the cranial radiology showed significant lesions but signs and symptoms were much subdued. Disseminated TB is defined as the presence of two or more non-contiguous sites resulting from hematogenous dissemination of *MTB*, occurring as a result of progressive primary infection or reactivation of a latent focus with subsequent spread. (14) Our patient had involvement of lung, lymph node and CNS, so was diagnosed as a case of disseminated TB. According to the TBM classification (7) she was a definitive TBM case with a diagnostic score of 16.

According to the RNTCP Updated Pediatric TB Guidelines 2019 on treatment of CNS TB (5) in children the intensive phase is of 2 months with four drugs i.e. Rifampicin (R), Isoniazid (H), Pyrazinamide (Z), Ethambutol (E) and an extended continuation phase of 8 months with three drugs i.e. RHE. Concomitant use of corticosteroids is recommended in all children with TBM regardless of the disease severity. Steroids are postulated to decrease the harmful effects of the immune response and lowers the incidence of hydrocephalus and brain infarction. (14) Dosage of prednisolone 1-2 mg/kg/day or dexamethasone 0.6 mg/kg/day or its equivalent is used for 4 weeks and then tapered over next 4 weeks. Steroids induce a rapid clinical improvement in sensorium, relief of headache and brings CSF values to normal levels. Isoniazid interferes competitively with pyridoxine metabolism by inhibiting the formation of the active form of the vitamin, and hence often results in peripheral neuropathy. Earlier supplementation was indicated only in high risk groups but now with the recommended increase in dose of isoniazid, pyridoxine in the dose of 10mg per day is given to all. (5)

CONCLUSION

A clinician must maintain a high index of suspicion for multi-site involvement with the diagnosis of TB, as it can be widely disseminated with subtle presentation as in our case. Clinical & radiological evaluation at follow up becomes important in CNS TB as tuberculomas may develop or increase even during the course of treatment. Timely investigations and management can decrease the considerably high morbidity and mortality associated with CNS TB.

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REFERENCES

1. **Rock RB, Olin, Baker CA, Molitor TW, Peterson PK.** Central nervous system Tuberculosis: pathogenesis and clinical aspects. *Clinical Microbiology Reviews.* 2008; 21: 243-261.
2. **Israni AV, Dave DA, Mandal A, Singh A, Sahi PK, Das RR, et al.** Tubercular meningitis in children: clinical, pathological, and radiological profile and factors associated with mortality. *J Neurosci Rural Pract* 2016;7:400-4.
3. **Cruz AT, Starke JR.** Clinical manifestation of tuberculosis in children. *Paediatric Respiratory Reviews.* 2007.8:107-117.
4. **WHO.** Global Tuberculosis Report. 2020. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/336069/9789240013131-eng.pdf>. Accessed: 28 Feb 2021.
5. **Updated IAP RNTCP Ped TB Guidelines 2019;** Developed by Revised National Tuberculosis Control and Indian Academy of Pediatrics; Central TB division, Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, New Delhi, India 2019;1-87.
6. **Rich AR, McCordock HA.** The pathogenesis of tuberculous meningitis. *Bull Johns Hopkins Hosp.*1933; 52:5-37.
7. **Marais S, Thwaites G, Schoeman JF, Torok ME, Misra UK, Prasad K, et al.** Tuberculous meningitis: A uniform case definition for use in clinical research. *Lancet Infect Dis* 2010;10:803-12.
8. **Chang K, Lu W, Wang J, Zhang K, Jia S, Li F, et al.** Rapid and effective diagnosis of tuberculosis and rifampicin resistance with Xpert MTB/RIF assay: a meta-analysis. *J Infect* 2012;64:580-8.
9. **Aulakh R, Chopra S.** Pediatric tubercular meningitis: A review. *J Pediatr Neurosci* 2018;13:373-82
10. **Chatterjee S.** Brain tuberculomas, tubercular meningitis, and post-tubercular hydrocephalus in children. *J Pediatr Neurosci.* 2011;6(Suppl 1):S96-S100.
11. **Elder NC.** Extra pulmonary tuberculosis. A review. *Arch Fam Med* 1992; 1: 91-8.
12. **Pauranik A, Behari M, Maheshwari MC.** Appearance of tuberculoma during treatment of tuberculous meningitis. *Jpn J Med.* 1987;26:332-4
13. **Pretell EJ, Martinot C, Jr, Garcia HH, Alvarado M, Bustos JA, Martinot C.** Cysticercosis Working Group in Peru. Differential diagnosis between cerebral tuberculosis and neurocysticercosis by magnetic resonance spectroscopy. *J Comput Assist Tomogr.* 2005;29:112-4.
14. **Khan FY, Dosa K, Fuad A, Ibrahim W, Alaini A, Osman L, et al.** Disseminated tuberculosis among adult patients admitted to Hamad general hospital, Qatar: A five year hospital based study. *Mycobact Dis.* 2016;6:212.
15. **INDEX-TB GUIDELINES -** Guidelines on extra-pulmonary tuberculosis for India. Central TB Division, MOHFW. GOI. 2016. Available from: <https://tbcindia.gov.in/showfile.php?lid=3245>. Accessed: 28 Feb 2021.